

**FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF PREGNANCY AND CHILDBIRTH
IN WOMEN WITH EPILEPSY.**

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Abstract. The relevance of the problem of pregnancy in women with epilepsy is beyond doubt due to the widespread prevalence of the disease, severe social and economic stigmatization not only for the patient and his relatives but also for society as a whole.

Key words: problem of pregnancy, women ,epilepsy

Purpose: We aimed to study the characteristics of the course of pregnancy and childbirth in women with epilepsy and to conduct a comparative analysis of the course of pregnancy and childbirth in women with epilepsy with a planned and unplanned pregnancy and healthy women in labor.

Methods: The work was carried out in the departments of neurology and obstetrics and gynecology of the Tashkent Medical Academy. Under observation were 60 pregnant women with various forms of epilepsy, disease duration from 1 to 25 years, as well as 20 practically healthy pregnant women and their offspring. Recruitment to the main group was carried out as the pregnant women were admitted to the hospital.

Results: In the anamnesis of patients, in addition to childhood infections, there are neuro infections: influenza - in 25 (31.25%), meningoencephalitis - in 3 (3.75%), purulent otitis media - in 5 (6.25%), chronic tonsillitis - in 16 (20%) women. Traumatic brain injury of varying severity was detected in 30 (37.5%) patients, pathology of the perinatal period (asphyxia, vacuum extractor, birth injuries) - in 8 (10%) patients, febrile convulsions - in 7 (8.75 %) of patients. This pregnancy in 17 (21.25%) women is planned, in the rest - not. 12 (15%) patients were registered in the PND. Of the bad habits, smoking was noted before pregnancy and during pregnancy (49 women - 61.25%). Burdened heredity for epilepsy occurred in 5 (6.25%) women. Childbirth was the first in 57 (71.25%) women, repeated in 23 (28.75%) women. In 72 (90%) cases, delivery occurred on time, premature - 7 (8.7%), late - 1 (1.3%).

The age of pregnant women with epilepsy ranged from 17 to 40 years and averaged 25.7 ± 5.3 years. It seemed interesting to us to analyze the change in the frequency of epileptic seizures in 9 (23.7%) pregnant women on monotherapy

in the dynamics of pregnancy. Thus, in 29 (76.3%) patients, drug remission of the disease occurred. In 9 (23.7%) women, single partial seizures were noted with an increase in them in 15.8% during pregnancy and a subsequent decrease in the postpartum period to 10%.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that it is preferable to manage pregnant women with epilepsy on monotherapy, despite the teratogenic effect of all drugs. Dynamic joint monitoring by a neurologist and an obstetrician-gynecologist using the entire range of non-invasive methods for monitoring the course of pregnancy helps prevent adverse pregnancy outcomes..

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